

Academician in the application of the history of Uzbekistan The place of the scientific heritage of V. V. Bartold.

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Annotation: *This article tells about the coverage of the history of Uzbekistan in the scientific heritage left by the famous orientalist, scholar of Central Asian history, author of many scientific works, Academician Vasily Vladimirovich Barthold.*

Key words: *Islamic civilization, Orientalist, V.V. Bartold, Mongol invasion, I. Umnyakov*

When the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev visited the area where the Center of Islamic Civilization of Uzbekistan will be built on June 15, 2019, he said, "Everyone glorifies their history. But there is no such rich history as in our country. We need to study this heritage in depth and be able to convey it to our people and the world," he emphasized [1].

The research of the history of Uzbekistan reached a new level at the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century. By this time, European orientalists became more interested in the history of the country. The history of Uzbekistan from the earliest times to the beginning of the 20th century was widely studied on the basis of fundamental research. The regions of Uzbekistan with a rich history have long attracted the attention of world historians. Interest in the history of these regions by local and international researchers, identifying the aspects that need to be studied, and finding solutions to the identified issues, scientific research is still going on rapidly. A skilled source scholar, academician V.V. Bartold (1869-1930) is also one of the orientalists who showed enthusiasm in studying the history of the regions of Uzbekistan.

V.V. The scope of Barthold's scientific interests is very wide, and his works cover the medieval history of the Near and Middle East, Central Asia, the history of Islam, the history of the Arab Caliphate, the history and philology of Iran and Afghanistan, historical geography, China and The history of Transcaucasia is covered by the philology and ethnography of the Turkic and Mongolian peoples, Muslim epigraphy and numismatics, source studies, Russian and world oriental studies [2].

V.V. Bartold paid special attention to the periodical importance and substantive aspects of a number of sources in the coverage of issues of the history of the regions of Uzbekistan, and was able to use relevant sources effectively. V.V. Bartold knew Arabic, Persian, and Turkish languages perfectly, he was able to easily translate manuscripts written in these languages and had no difficulty in using sources. There were also places where Barthold was critical of the information given in the sources. Academician V. V. Bartold says that there is not enough information about the pre-Islamic history of these regions.[3]

Barthold's academician I. Yu. In the words of Krachkovsky, it would be appropriate to acknowledge that he looked at "the entire Muslim world on a large geographical and chronological scale, in a wide area" [4] with deep and consistent attention.

Historian scientist B. Ahmedov states the following about the scientific heritage of V.V. Barthold in Turkestan in his work: "Academic Vasilii Vladimirovich Barthold (1869-1930) wrote "Mog" about the history, social, economic and cultural life of Turkestan in the ancient and middle ages. "Turkistan during the conquest of Turkestan" (1900), "Information about the condition of the lands in the lower reaches of the Aral Sea and Amudarya from ancient times to the 17th century" (1902), "From the history of irrigation of Turkestan" (1914), "Great bek and his era" (1918), "Cotton cultivation in Central Asia from ancient times to the arrival of the Russians" (1924), "Cultural life of Turkestan" (1927) have dozens of great scientific and practical value. He is a great Orientalist scholar who wrote down his works. Suffice it to say that almost half of the 685 works published by the scientist, 320 to be precise, are devoted to the analysis of the history, socio-economic and cultural life of Turkestan."[5]

The study of the scientific heritage of V.V. Bartol can be divided into three periods: the period before the October coup in Russia, the literature of the Soviet period and the period of independence. Each period differs from each other both in terms of number and content.

The historiography of the first period can be expressed mainly by reviews and articles in scientific publications prepared to show V.V. Barthold as a scholar of the history and culture of the peoples of the East and draw attention to his works and scientific activities. At this time, V. V. Bartold determined the political nature of

studying the ancient East based on classical texts. At the same time, his report prepared by the history-philology department of the Imperial Academy of Sciences for 1914 is also noteworthy [6].

In the second period (1918-1991), a high level of interest in researching the life and scientific activity of V.V. Bartold can be observed.

According to the list of works of Academician W. V. Barthold (this list includes works written from 1892 to 1930, compiled with the personal supervision and additions of the scientist), 136 of his 350 main works were published during the period of the former Union power in 1918-1930. His works on the history of Central Asia are in the first place.

It was in the second period, that is, from 1918 to 1991, that a circle of historians was formed who studied his works. Among them are A. Yu. Yakubovsky, I. I. Umnyakov, A. A. Semenov, B. V. Lunin, N. N. Tumanovich and others.

Among Bartold's followers, A.Yu. Yakubovsky continued his teacher's work devoted to the study of Amir Timur and the history of the Timurid period. A.Yu. Yakubovsky has been leading the Sug-Tajik archeological expedition since 1945. Yakubovsky about Barthold, "Barthold's legacy, his numerous works are imbued with progressive ideas. It stood above the widespread racial theory and discriminatory attitude towards the peoples of the East and their history among the bourgeois scholars of the late 19th and early 20th centuries.

I.I. Umnyakov is also one of the scientists who made a great contribution to the study of the scientific heritage of V.V. Barthold. It can be said that Umnyakov's work on the biography of V.V. Bartold was the first detailed information of its time. One of the important studies of I.I. Umnyakov, the book "Annotirovannaya bibliografiya trudov V.V. Bartolda" published in 1976 is also noteworthy [7]. It also includes republished and translated scientific works of the scientist. By studying this book, one can get complete information about the scientific heritage of V. V. Bartold.

B.V. Lunin "Jizn i deyatelnost academica V.V. Bartolda. In his monograph "Srednyaya Aziya v dorevolutsionnom i sovetskom vostokovedenii", he highly appreciated the life of V.V. Bartold and his contribution to the study of the history of Central Asia.

In this book, the author considered the life and work of B.V. Bartold directly in connection with the history of the development of oriental studies of the country.

After the period of independence, all opportunities were created for an objective study of academician V.V. Bartold's scientific heritage. It can be noted here that the scientific heritage of V.V. Bartold was selected as an object of study in a number of candidate theses.

Studying the scientific heritage left by V.V. Bartold, an orientalist who studied not only Uzbekistan, but also the ancient and medieval history of Central Asia, and the effective use of them in his scientific work, in the illumination of the historiography of Uzbekistan by scientific researchers, historians-scientists plays a major role.

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